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Relevance of systematic approach for management development

Abstract

The paper argues the importance of a more formalised and structured approach to learning. Both formal and informal development processes are enhanced only if those processes are structured and planned through the accurate identification of needs, the establishment of objectives, the use of appropriate techniques, and meaningful assessment mechanisms. Identifying what managers want through self-diagnosis provides the focus on what is to be learnt. Setting goals directs managers towards the appropriate direction, while goal sharing with others may be useful in providing mutual support and challenge. Designing learning processes based on goals and appropriate resources and support for learning enables managers to achieve those goals. Finally, by reflection, success and failure can be assessed. This provides information on whether learning was on track or whether goals have to be revised. The paper, further, emphasises the need for organisational support systems for what individuals learnt from the development interventions to flow freely within the organisations to be captured and used by other organisational members.

Keywords: Management development, Systematic approach

Introduction

The term 'systematic approach' is interpreted as a logical relationship between sequential phases in the development effort (Buckley and Caple, 1990). In this context, management development (MD) effort could be viewed as an interdependent and interrelated process. Each phase of the total process is a sub-process of the entire process. Therefore, the sub-processes are interdependent, interrelated, and stand individually, but when connected, form more than the sum of their parts (ILO, 1986; Wills, 1998a). Hence, this view stresses a concern for the total system rather than for the objectives of any single component (Goldstein, 1974). Writers argue that the systematic concept is sound and can be used as a heuristic device and an approximation to reality (Bratton and Gold, 1999). The model serves to highlight the problems that need to be overcome at each phase by refining techniques. It is apparent from the literature that many scholars view development effort as a process or series of logical phases, and a close

study of these shows that they all contain the same phases, even though they may be presented in different formats (Buckley and Caple, 1990). However, generally there is an agreement among all writers that formal development effort should declare certain learning objectives, use a variety of learning methods to reach the objectives, and apply some kind(s) of evaluation/validation at the end of the programmes. Although the systematic approach places evaluation as the last phase of the model, a number of writers have pointed out the value of evaluation at each phase of the process (Bratton and Gold, 1999; Brinkerhoff, 1987). In this context, the systems and systematic approach use feedback to continually modify the processes (Goldstein, 1974). From this perspective, development programmes are never finished products: they are continually adaptive to information that indicates whether they meet the stated objectives. Therefore, this view of development effort is the best place to start if quick and significant improvements are expected (Wills, 1998b).

Because of the following reasons, the writer feels that a systematic approach is needed for MD.

- In providing development opportunities for managers, identification of needs is vital.
- Better administration of any development activity and the validation of outcomes are also vital when MD is considered as an investment. Therefore, the systematic approach facilitates monitoring the progress of MD activities.
- The systematic approach is goal-oriented (to produce results for the organisation and/or for the learners), with the results of each phase being used by the next phase. Typically, each phase provides ongoing evaluation feedback to other phases in order to improve the overall system. Therefore, an advantage of adopting this concept in MD is that it allows establishing checkpoints to keep each phase on track, under control, and produce the required outputs. These checkpoints can be established at the beginning, during, and at the end of the process. The checkpoints at the beginning answer the question of whether the correct outputs will be produced. The checkpoints during the process answer the question of whether the correct outputs are being produced. The checkpoints at the end answer the question of whether the correct outputs have been produced (Wills, 1998b). Therefore, this process can be considered a helpful means of preventing or solving problems.
- The systematic approach also involves line management in the process by making them establish development needs, assess results, etc (Tavernier, 1971).

- The systematic approach is applicable to any organisation regardless of organisational context (Patrick, 1992), though the rigidity of the process could vary among managers and workers.
- The MD effort could vary in its scope, nature, and patterns from one organisation to another. Yet, as Esterby-Smith & Ashton (1979) state, it is apparently easy to transpose the formal objectives of MD from one organisation to another.

Relevance of systematic approach for contemporary views of management development

The leading ideas in management have changed over time (Megginson et al., 1999). These changes reflect a realisation that the circumstances are different, and new needs are dominating in the organisation. The above-mentioned systematic approach dominated in the management development practice from the mid 1960s to the mid-1970s. According to Megginson and Pedler (as in Megginson, 1994), this systematic approach became significant due to skills shortages identified during that period. Based on the above context, contemporary literature reveals that in developing managers, the separation of formal processes from informal processes literally takes MD away from the reality of managerial work (Megginson and Whitaker, 1999; Megginson, 1994; Marsick and Watkins, 1997). Hence, in the development process, both informal and formal development processes have to be utilised. Formal processes include institutionally sponsored, planned, and deliberate processes, which are often monitored and controlled by people and forces other than the individual manager involved. Informal processes, on the other hand, are by-products of other organisational activities, such as task accomplishment or interpersonal interaction, and managers may not set out intentionally and explicitly to learn something through pre-planned means. However, the most significant feature of informal development incidents is that, although informal development opportunities almost always take place naturally, managers are not always conscious that they are in developmental experiences at all. Therefore, informal development incidents are the tip of an iceberg in two senses. First, they are a tiny proportion of the full range of incidents from the managerial work that provide learning experiences. Second, they are the tip of an iceberg for any particular individual. Therefore, though informal, accidental experiences are widely present and often provide the deepest and richest learning, they are often badly identified and, as a consequence, insufficiently used. Therefore, informal learning has to be deliberately encouraged by an organisation. Organisations can provide kinds of challenges that will provide opportunities to develop new skills/abilities. Though conventional development activities that are based on

internal or external means still have a role to play, informal and incidental learning is also important. Both formal and informal development processes are enhanced only if those processes are structured and planned through the accurate identification of needs and objectives, the use of appropriate techniques, and meaningful assessment mechanisms. Therefore, there is an important role for a more formalised and structured approach to learning. By using the systematic approach, formal development activities could be designed in such a way that they are valuable experiences for the learner, and those are useful revision methods for existing staff in becoming mentors. In the case of informal learning, individual involvement is vital. Individual managers have to identify their own purposes for learning. Ultimately, disciplined reflection leads to deeper learning. However, in this process, organisational backing and support from peer groups are also important. In this connection, works by Marsick and Watkins (1997), Mumford (1997), Megginson (1994), Megginson and Whitaker (1999), and Cunningham (1999) stress that individuals with their bosses have to plan the development process. Further, professional bodies such as the Institute of Personal Development, UK, also ask members to plan their continuous development. The planning involves asking members what they do, what they might do in the future, and what resources and methods they might use. Then they have to specify their development opportunities, detail their action plans, and keep development records (Megginson, 1994). Hence, based on the contemporary view, too, to have success in personal development, the individual and the boss have to plan the development. Hence, identification, designing, implementation, and evaluation are vital.

On the other hand, one of the problems with the development effort is that it is not always planned and conducted systematically in a way that reflects best practices in development design and delivery. In other words, the operational quality of development effort is sometimes lacking (Megginson et al., 1993). Therefore, though one can identify disadvantages of the systematic approach, the writer feels that this approach is an ongoing, flexible, and results-oriented approach that helps organisations to link MD objectives with present and future organisational problems and strategies. Further, it guides individuals in their own development. Therefore, organisations can use these approaches in MD as a blueprint or as a best practice.

Therefore, the rest of the paper places emphasis on describing how both formal and informal management development could benefit from the systematic approach that comprises development needs identification, setting objectives, designing and planning management

development activities, implementation of management development activities, and transfer, validation, and evaluation of development activities.

Development needs identification

Needs identification and needs evaluation/validation are two essential activities connected to MD (Wills, 1998; Harrison, 1992). Many writers state that the need for identification is the identification of the gap between requirements of the job and present capabilities of the individual, and this is the gap that has to be filled by MD (Storey and Sission, 1993; Mumford et al, 1981; Armstrong, 1991; Boydell, 1971; Arnold et al., 1991). Further, almost all researchers have agreed with the view that the identification of MD needs to follow a logical sequence from the corporate level to the individual level (Wills, 1998b; Mole, 2000; Mathis and Jackson, 1994; Boydell, 1976; Goldstein, 1974; Stewart, 1994). To make the process effective, the development requirements identified need to be evaluated/validated to identify those individuals who need development opportunities to ensure that development activities are both appropriate and necessary. Further, it is also useful to estimate the impact of the MD workload and to prepare an MD plan (Bratton and Gold, 1999; Wills, 1998b).

In the case of informal learning, individual managers have to identify prospective learning opportunities and should subsequently review the extent to which he/she has taken advantage of them (Mumford, 1997). Such identification is always looking back retrospectively to learn from past experience. Essentially, the experience resides in a good retrospective review or a good analysis of prospective experience. Those are managerial activities from which some deliberate learning is derived from conscious thought and discussion. Every time what needs to be learnt should be linked to work situations. At the core of the leading idea of linking learning to work is the importance of stating the needs and aspirations of the learner. This empowers the learner to begin learning by thinking about what they want to master, improve, or change (Megginson et al., 1993). For instance, managers can undertake self-diagnosis and clarify what they want to do. This may help managers in focusing on what needs to be learnt.

Though managers create learning experiences by thinking and reviewing normal managerial activities purely “in the head”, they can also be found by reviewing various kinds of (mainly written) material (Mumford, 1997). Some of such written materials are job description; activity list or daily/weekly reminder of things to do; work diary that may simply indicate some of the most important events on daily basis; a learning log, where a manager deliberately keeps a

review of learning experiences and opportunities; discussions with colleagues, where one or more colleagues identify similar activities and experience which may provide learning; individual discussions with boss, where some specific activity is related to a learning opportunity. Therefore, individuals have to make an effort in the identification of learning incidents. In the planning process, personal development plans that are developed in concert between managers, their superiors, and often external learning facilitators, play a vital part (Mumford, 1997; Marsick and Watkins, 1997).

Setting objectives

Once needs have been identified, specific and clear objectives can be established that can be used to design development activities and validate/evaluate the outcomes. The objectives of development activities should relate back to the development needs identified in the needs analysis. Therefore, objectives are an essential tool for the developers of the development activities, the providers of those activities, and the learners (Wills, 1998b). The objectives need to be specific and unambiguous in stating the changes expected in terms of the organisational and the individual performance (Scholl and Brownell, 1983; Wills, 1998b).

In the case of informal learning, too, experience is not educational unless it is purposive. The objective or purpose guides the process of learning. When the purpose is clear, managers can observe surrounding conditions better; they can learn from the knowledge of what has happened in similar situations in the past. Further, the purpose guides to learn from the knowledge that is obtained by recollection, and from information, advice, and warnings of those who have a wider experience. Therefore, most often having objectives in incidental learning is vital.

As mentioned in the earlier phase, managers can set the objectives based on the materials they used to identify learning situations, such as job description, work diary, learning log, individual discussion with boss, etc. In setting objectives, it is much more likely to involve other people, probably the manager and the boss in most situations, or perhaps the manager and one or more colleagues. The discussion of options, prospective learning, and retrospective learning is likely to be enhanced by checking them out with other people. It is partly through this process of openness, sharing, and partnership that some of the weaknesses of learning from experience can be reduced.

Designing and planning management development activities

Not all MD interventions call for straightforward transfer of knowledge/skills; therefore, the most appropriate development interventions have to be selected or designed (Mole, 2000). The instructional constraints imposed by what, who, and how of the design of development activities. The first line of questioning centres on the development method itself, with the human resource professionals asking *what* limitations will be placed on the development needs by the method selected (Warren, 1979). The second line of investigation in defining constraints is to decide *who* will conduct the intervention (Wills, 1998b). Third, it is needed to identify those constraints imposed on the intervention by the organisation's approach to the implementation of the action, and *how* the intervention will be handled in the real working environment of the organisation. De Meuse and Tornow (1996) state that in developing employees, the focus must shift to activities that favour career planning and continuous development. Above all, it is necessary to make adjustments to the development plan and prioritise the candidates.

In the case of informal learning, one of the features of managerial experience as a learning process is that managers have to plan/pre-decide informal learning. However, learning should not be separated from experience. Therefore, learning has to be tied to real-life problems and experience. Though learning takes place "just in time" while struggling with a challenge, this cannot happen without time to learn, feedback, and other forms of assistance (Marsick and Watkins, 1997). According to Marsick and Watkins (1997), real-life challenges are also woven consciously into classroom activities. Therefore, computer-based technology has often been used as well to aid in problem solving, self-directed learning, and interactive online dialogue. Further, there are tools that have been created to enhance planning for learning that is tied to job challenges.

Implementation of management development activities

The selection of appropriate development interventions does not ensure the success of the development effort. Although implementation is the culmination of all the efforts that have been put into the previous phases, it should be remembered that, as far as the rest of the organisation is concerned, this is only the start of the change process (Wills, 1998b). However, if an intervention did not reach the expected level of achievements, it is often not that they are conceptually flawed or poorly designed, but because they are badly administered. In

administering development interventions, both pre and post-administration requirements have to be considered (Wills, 1998).

In the case of informal learning, managers may have no choice about the managerial experience. However, managers have to learn from them. According to writers, failure to learn from experience might not be the result of deliberate and conscious avoidance but simply failure to recognise the opportunity or ignorance about how to learn from it most effectively (Mumford, 1997). When managers are unable to learn immediately as they are faced with work situations, they have to use these in retrospect, where managers look back on a particularly powerful managerial experience and more or less consciously register learning from it.

However, whether learning is provoked by events or by others, a manager's insight alone is insufficient. They need organisational support, which encourages individuals to grow, accepts individuals who have changed, and promotes the retention of new behaviours (Marsick and Watkins, 1997). Therefore, facilitation is vital at this point of the process. When learning is unintentional, facilitators have added tasks, such as dealing with the emotions generated by a surprise and behaving ethically. However, in most situations, managerial learning is intentional; therefore, the task of the facilitator is primarily to help self-directed learners be more productive in their learning projects. On the other hand, according to the human resource development perspective, what an individual manager has learnt has to flow freely within the organisation (Marsick and Watkins, 1997). What is most important is that such individual learning has to flow from the individuals, and those have to be captured and used by other members of the organisation. Hence, in this process, developing an environment conducive to learning is vital.

Therefore, learning has to be pursued consciously and deliberately for profit (Kolb, 1996). Managers and organisations should budget time specifically to learn from their experience. For example, when important meetings are held or important decisions are made, time should be set aside to critique and learn from these events (Kolb, 1996). On the other hand, managers have to have the freedom to influence outcomes by taking risks and doing things differently (Megginson and Whitaker, 1999).

Transfer, validation, and evaluation of development activities

According to writers, the final phase of the systematic approach brings MD into a full cycle. This phase has to be considered in terms of transfer, validation, and evaluation. The first aspect, the transfer of learning, ensures that the learning is transferred into the business. Management development has no impact on the business unless the skills are used back in the workplace (Warren, 1979). The second aspect is known as the validation of development interventions, and it is the process of ensuring that programmes meet and continue to meet their stated objectives (Wills, 1998b; Martin, 1968). Validation is an internal check on the development activities, primarily at the individual level - whether the participants have reached the required standard and their reactions to the interventions (Wills, 1998b). The third aspect, evaluation, ensures that development activities have had the desired effect. Evaluation is a set of information-gathering techniques. Mathis and Jackson (1994) and Wills (1998b) argue that because development is both time-consuming and costly, evaluation should be an integral part of the programme. However, evaluation is not required to be done after each and every development intervention. Validation is normally sufficient to get the required information on development interventions. Then, finally, the programmes need to be revised to incorporate the changes identified during the validation and evaluation (Wills, 1998b).

In the case of informal learning, as explained under setting objectives, experience is not educational unless it is purposive. A significant feature of incidental learning is that it occurs naturally. However, managers have to analyse their interpretations; otherwise, their false assumptions can lead them to inaccurate conclusions. Reflection is the primary tool to trigger learning from experience. Disciplined reflection, challenging one's assumptions and comfortable ways of thinking, leads to deeper learning. Unintentional learning can lead to intentional learning, only if it is identified by reflection.

To make the informal and incidental learning more effective, managers can maintain learning logs, they can keep journals, or they can review backward. These are some of the tools that can be used in the learning process. Learning log can be used to record experience, what happened, conclusions, the actions individuals will take, and by when (Megginson, 1994). The learning log has to be reviewed from time to time to see how the individual has progressed with his/her actions. Success or failure highlighted by this review may lead to another entry into the learning log. Keeping a record of life in a diary or journal is perhaps a key method of logging learning.

It can include reviews of one's own experience, or references to read, or ideas that have come across. Such tools provide vital information in the process of reflection.

Unless considerable effort is put into development interventions, development, at best, is random and haphazard or may not be what is best for the organisation. Therefore, transfer, validation, and evaluation have to be thoroughly considered. In informal learning, reflection is the most important. Experience can lead to intentional learning only if identified by reflection. Managers may need organisational support in the process.

Overall, though planning, both formal and informal learning, enables individuals to nurture learning strategically and to take advantage of a wider range of learning strategies that might otherwise be overlooked, it should not be forgotten that there might be a range of factors that create problems. First, the process requires motivation, attitude, flexibility, and propensity to learn from the individual employee. Learners have to remain open to alternative frames of a problem, seek competing explanations, adopt an attitude of experimentation, and try on new behaviours for their own development. Second, the nature of the managers' jobs should offer opportunities to actually use the skills and competencies the manager has obtained. Therefore, the addition of new responsibilities, chances to experience jobs in other sections through planned job rotational schemes, are all relevant to the need to provide jobs that challenge the employee and offer new and interesting work experience. Third, organisations have to provide an environment that is conducive to learning. Organisations have to encourage, nurture, and support the development process, and have to promote the retention of new behaviours to make learning so much more effective and valuable. Organisations have to budget resources, especially time for development activities. Only through organisational support systems will what individuals have learnt from the development interventions flow freely within the organisations to be captured and used by other organisational members.

Conclusion

There is an important role for a more formalised and structured approach to learning. Though conventional development programmes that are based on internal or external means still have a role to play, informal and incidental learning is also important. Both formal and informal development processes are enhanced only if those processes are structured and planned through the accurate identification of needs, the establishment of objectives, the use of appropriate techniques, and meaningful assessment mechanisms. Identifying what managers want through

self-diagnosis provides the focus on what is to be learnt. Setting goals directs managers towards the appropriate direction, while goal sharing with others may be useful in providing mutual support and challenge. Designing learning processes based on goals and appropriate resources and support for learning enables managers to achieve those goals. Finally, by reflection, success and failure can be assessed. This provides information on whether learning was on track or whether goals have to be revised. Therefore, development planning, like the systematic approach to MD, is a cycle, where each phase provides inspiration and guidance to the other. Therefore, managers have to integrate this into their lives on a continuous basis. In the learning process, facilitators, peers, other colleagues, and managers from other organisations can be great sources of knowledge. Hence, organisations have to provide an environment that is conducive to learning, where learning is encouraged, nurtured, and supported.

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